

SOUND AWARENESS ACTIVITIES TOWARDS A TOOLKIT FOR UNDERSTANDING PERSONAL SOUNDSCAPE EXPERIENCES

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We studied older adults' home sound environments through experience sampling and cultural probes focused on deep listening. This research aims to guide AI soundscape system design. We used deep listening exercises, sound journals, memory-association prompts, and soundscape assessments to gather data.

A. SOUND AWARENESS ACTIVITIES OVERVIEW & EXAMPLE RESPONSES

1. EXPERIENCE SAMPLING METHOD (ESM) SCHEDULE

Activity notifications were distributed across seven days using four designated time periods to optimise participant engagement while preventing fatigue. We incorporated controlled randomization within these periods to maintain variety in the notification schedule.

Future iterations could implement personalised scheduling to accommodate individual participants' work and lifestyle patterns, potentially increasing response rates.

Example schedule activities are coded with icons to show you what they are related to.

Soundscape Activity Memory Activity

2. MOMENTARY SOUNDSCAPE JUDGEMENT

Participants recorded and rated soundscapes via the smartphone app, assessing soundscape dimensions, emotional impact, and personal reflections. Each assessment included mood data, with unlimited optional repetitions over one week.

Try to identify all the different sounds you could hear, describe these in whatever way you like

P3: "The wind is blowing hard and stormy."

P5: "Classical music on the radio, cutting meat with my husband's knife and fork."

3. EVERYDAY OBJECT ASSOCIATIONS

Task investigating how individuals connect everyday objects with sounds, memories, and emotions. Through participant engagement with common items, this method reveals personal values and sonic associations while contributing to design research.

Please tell us about your everyday object.

Looking at your everyday object, imagine what sounds belong with it.

P3: "This little angel and that pebble painted by my youngest sister, which I got a couple of years ago from her, give me a lot of beautiful memories because we ride bicycles together during the summer. Those are always very fun moments, and so we build memories that bring a lot of virtue and pleasure."

P3: "These two objects bring back so many memories. We cycled in the sun in nature. We heard birds. We heard rain. We heard trees blowing in the wind."

4. MEMENTO ASSOCIATION

A task exploring how individuals relate to meaningful objects and their associated sounds. Participants describe a personal artifact and explore its sonic connections, generating data on sensory experiences and emotional responses.

Looking at your memento, imagine what sounds belong with it.

P2: "I associate this vase with silence, a scarce oral choice with a clear voice of our son... then end up in the hustle and bustle of the city... thinking of sounds early some moments of searching... was a bit difficult... especially by the apparent lack of sounds... what a feeling of wonder, peace, confidence in our twenties... this choice touched me... memory of this day still feels special..."

5. SOUND JOURNALLING

Sound Journaling involves capturing and reflecting on interesting sounds encountered throughout the week, noting thoughts and emotions associated with them, and answering context and mood questions.

Please reflect on why this sound was interesting or meaningful to you. Mention why you chose to record this sound, along with any thoughts or emotions associated with it.

P4: I think I heard the sound of a charcoal fire, and I enjoyed it until a car drove through the street, and I was thrown back into reality. I heard, but couldn't look at, the sound recordings — probably a couple of geese high in the air. Those guys are getting ready for their overwintering in Spain and even Morocco, while we're just staying home around the cozy warmth of the stove.

6. PEN & PAPER ACTIVITIES

Some of the activity suggestions we designed to enhance participants' sonic attention, explore sense of place, and states of mind.

WISH CARDS
Write about the things you would like to improve or change about your sonic environments and the sounds of the world around you. We have provided some wish cards for this purpose. These cards have prompts that you can answer, including one that asks you to imagine a technology that would create your ideal soundscape.

FIND HIDDEN SOUNDS
Hearing gets to places where sight cannot. Ears see through walls and around corners. When something is hidden, sound will reveal its location and meaning. Make a list of all the sounds you can think of that come from hidden places, sounds that are made by objects you have never seen. Here are some examples: water in a drainpipe, wind, thunder, an echo, stomach growling. We have provided the "Soundscape Notepad" in the probe pack to note down your findings as you do the task.

B. PARTICIPANT FEEDBACK

What did you like about your participation in the study?

P5: "Curiosity. Fun scattering through the day. Getting to know myself better. Feeling asked for my opinion. Being seen."

P1: "The activities"
The method exposed how residents actively manage their sound environments:

P2: "It was fun to discover and interact with my environment through a new angle (hearing)."

How did the study support your experiences around sound and conscious listening?

P7: "listening to details provided by day-to-day actions. For example, how the activity: making coffee can be described in detail by listening to the successive actions"

P2: "Listening consciously and pausing for a moment for sounds that suddenly present themselves sometimes broadens and colours the situation in a pleasant way..."

C. INSPIRATIONS

Hwang, E., & Lim, Y. (2020). Tuning into the Sound: Discovering Motivational Enablers for Self-Therapy Design. Synergy - DRS International Conference 2020. Design Research Society Conference.

Ingold, T. (2011). Being alive: Essays on movement, knowledge and description. Routledge.

Oleksik, G., Frohlich, D., Brown, L. M., & Sellen, A. (2008). Sonic interventions: Understanding and extending the domestic soundscape. Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems.

Oliveros, P. (2005). Deep listening: A composer's sound practice. Deep Listening Publications.

Schafer, R. M. (1992). A sound education: 100 exercises in listening and sound-making. Indian River, Ont.: Arcana Editions.

Williams, A., & Coblenz, M. (2018). LISTENING TO THE CITY: Community Research and Action through Sound and Story. MIT Community Innovators Lab.

D. PROTOCOL & DATA

Full Protocol
<https://zenodo.org/records/14946672>

Pilot Data
<https://zenodo.org/records/14999348>

Embargoed until 01/09/25, access via t.deacon@surrey.ac.uk